

 Keywords:

#EOSC, #FAIR, #Interdisciplinary,
#KnowledgeGraphs, #COVID19, #COVID19data,
#ResearchCommunity, #EOSCinPractice

Interdisciplinary Approach to FAIR Metadata: Enabling Collaborative Science in the European Open Science Cloud

Enhancing cross-domain metadata interoperability, integration and impact on COVID-19 research across Science Clusters

The Project Involved

Within EO SC Future, the Science Project “COVID-19 metadata findability and interoperability in EO SC” (in short META-COVID) aimed to explore the importance of “contextual metadata” in the fields of Life Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities and to develop a framework for a metadata model characterising the research approach and workflow across research infrastructures. Contextual metadata are referring to a) information about the research process that generated the data, including descriptions of that process and the methodologies used, and b) information about the ‘inputs’ into the research process – e.g., grants, people, organisations, regulators, and research infrastructures and resources. The project is guided by three practical use cases in the field of COVID-19. One use case looking into enhancing the interoperability of the [ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository](#) and the [BBMRI-ERIC Directory](#), another looking into cross-linking information from the [CESSDA Data Catalogue](#) and the [ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository](#) and a final one focusing on designing an ontology for COVID-19 related topics as discussed in parliamentary debates and social media.

The Research Community

META-COVID involved two Science Clusters: Life Sciences represented by the partners ECRIN, BBMRI-ERIC, EATRIS and EU-Openscreen and Social Sciences and Humanities represented by CESSDA and CLARIN. In order to collect feedback and achieve alignment, META-COVID collaborated with other (EO SC) projects of relevance (e.g. EO SC-Life, BY-COVID, ISIDORE, EO SC4Cancer, FAIRCORE4EO SC, FAIR-IMPACT), members of the EO SC Task Force on Semantic Interoperability, actors involved in the EO SC Interoperability Framework and relevant RDA Working Groups. The outcomes of this project are of interest for researchers working on metadata, ontologies, and vocabularies.

The Challenge

Currently, there are metadata schemas (such as DataCite, or DDI) that can describe the concrete outputs of research, e.g., papers and datasets, but relatively little work has been done on finding a metadata schema for the research itself. The problem is that different disciplines have vastly different ways of organising research activities, for instance because of differences in funding models and mechanisms, or in requirements for approval, and thus differences in how and when research is split into discrete activities and labelled.

Maria Panagiotopoulou

Senior Project Manager at ECRIN

“For the first time, the META-COVID project brought together metadata experts from different research infrastructures in the fields of Life Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities with the aim of discussing interoperability of information on COVID-19 across domains. The project inventoried the different metadata schemas used by the research infrastructures, discussed the creation of a common “contextual metadata” framework and linked the different metadata catalogues with relevant EO SC work, such as onboarding them in the Marketplace or exploring the applicability of the EO SC Interoperability Framework.”

In addition, research efforts take place at a variety of scales, have varying requirements for pre-published protocols, use a huge range of different methodologies and workflows, and may even draw upon different underlying assumptions. Research design, approach, strategy and method are heavily influenced by the researchers’ epistemology and research philosophy. The type of the research (e.g., hypothesis testing versus hypothesis generating), the methodology chosen (e.g., experimental, survey, cohort, case study) and the research methods applied (e.g., type of sampling) are of major importance in understanding the data generated, and thus in supporting any secondary use of that data. Another issue to be solved is the integration of various sources of information related to parliamentary and social media metadata. Consequently, metadata should go beyond a description of the data itself to include the basic elements of the research process (“contextual metadata”).

The solution

The COVID-19 pandemic has generated a huge variety of research activities, studies and policies across both life sciences and social sciences and humanities: examples include genomic sequencing, assays of immune response, clinical trials, population health analyses, exploring vaccine hesitancy, investigating the role of social media, public debate and economic analyses of the impact of public policy issues (e.g., lockdown measures, imposed face masking). Potential insights from combining the data and conclusions from these different forms of research are, however, made more difficult by the lack of a common metadata framework with which to describe them.

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Even within one scientific cluster (e.g., SSHOC, EOSC-Life), the metadata landscape is heterogeneous and numerous domain-specific standards are applied (e.g. MIABIS for biobank information, DICOM for images). Developing widely applicable metadata is a key part of rendering data more valuable, by allowing them to be more easily found and characterised, regardless of the discipline in which they were generated. META-COVID inventoried the different metadata schemas used by the research infrastructures and generated a proposal for a framework to describe contextual metadata. As part of the work, Knowledge Graphs for [COVID-19](#) and for [Monkeypox](#) have been developed to represent complex scientific information.

EOSC service or tool used

The project leveraged the EOSC as a unique environment to collaborate with metadata experts from different scientific domains. The work around the EOSC Interoperability Framework impacted META-COVID and got impacted by it. In addition, a lot of the partners' metadata catalogues and tools have been made available through the EOSC marketplace, ensuring easy accessibility for users. Service providers benefited from receiving information about total views and downloads, enabling them to monitor the impact of their resources effectively. Project partners became also aware of and embedded in their work other products from the EOSC Marketplace such as the EGI-Notebooks, a horizontal service within EOSC, which allowed developers to work on personalized and secure remote servers without the need to install any software/tools on their local PCs.

Benefits and impact

META-COVID allowed for the first time a multidisciplinary discussion among metadata experts from different infrastructures in the Life Sciences and Social Sciences and Humanities on the FAIRness of metadata in their respective fields and interoperability issues across domains. The use cases within META-COVID will improve the discoverability of data objects related to COVID-19 across different research infrastructures. For example, ECRIN and BBMRI-ERIC are enriching their metadata catalogues so that information on biosamples can be linked to information about the clinical study that generated them.

Useful material related to this story

ECRIN

The development of a COVID-19 ontology to describe information from parliamentary debates and social media will also strengthen our knowledge on the impact of the different health policy measures on the population and lead to the informed design of future biomedical studies. The contextual metadata framework will inform other relevant initiatives such as [the European COVID-19 data portal](#).

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC is creating a multidisciplinary environment of Open Science practices, tools, data and services in which metadata interoperability across different scientific fields plays a crucial role for the findability of relevant data objects. EOSC facilitated collaboration and provided a platform for sharing resources and knowledge. It allowed the project team to host their resources in a centralised marketplace, making them easily accessible to the research community. Furthermore, EOSC services like EGI-Notebooks eliminated the need for local installations and provided a secure and personalised remote server environment for efficient and cost-effective knowledge graph creation.

Across disciplines

META-COVID is interdisciplinary by design. The project's approach of capturing "contextual" metadata was finetuned with diverse research infrastructures, spanning clinical research, biobanks, chemical biology, social media and parliamentary talks, social science surveys. Although the framework has been developed with COVID-19 in mind, there is nothing impeding its generalizability to other disease areas.

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